

TENSILE PROPERTY EVALUATION OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE-REINFORCED ALUMINIUM ALLOY

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ABSTRACT

A composite of aluminium alloy reinforced with continuous alumina-based fibres has been made by liquid metal infiltration. It is shown to be well consolidated with strong bonding between fibre and matrix, that is its Young's modulus matches 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions with ~ 130 GPa in the fibre direction and ~ 100 GPa in the transverse direction. The effect of fibre orientation on Poisson's ratio is then discussed. The yield stress was found to differ in longitudinal and transverse directions due to anisotropic residual matrix stresses. Strength in the longitudinal direction appeared to be affected by some reduction in fibre strength during composite manufacture, whereas transverse strength was controlled by the matrix, as expected with a strong fibre/matrix bond. Heat treatment increased yield stress and strength for both the longitudinal and transverse fibre orientations.

INTRODUCTION

Although the reinforcement of aluminium with continuous ceramic fibres offers, potentially, the greatest benefit as regards stiffness and strength, the composite with the unidirectional reinforcement then exhibits anisotropy with transverse properties determined essentially by the metal matrix. Nevertheless, improvements may be possible if a heat-treatable alloy is employed for the matrix and, indeed, data are available reporting progress in developing aluminium alloy-based composites which contain discontinuous reinforcements [1,2]. However, there is little information relating to the incorporation of continuous fibres in heat-treatable aluminium alloys, a situation which arises in the main from the lack of good quality, defect-free material for systematic evaluation.

The capability that we now have for fabricating, consistently, well-consolidated fibre composites has provided an opportunity for investigating this important class of material. This paper describes a study of heat-treatable aluminium alloy containing continuous fibres of alumina and discusses theoretical and practical aspects of the mechanical behaviour of the composite. The data are used to provide a clearer understanding of the role of fibre and matrix and of the effect of residual stresses on yielding behaviour.

EXPERIMENTAL

MATERIALS

Aluminium alloy (IADS 6061) of composition 1.0 wt% Mg, 0.8 wt% Si, 0.7 wt% Fe and 0.2 wt% Mn was used for the matrix. The reinforcement was continuous alumina-based fibre of $\sim 13 \mu\text{m}$ diameter, designated Altex (Sumitomo Chemicals, Japan). The composite was manufactured by liquid metal infiltration of a fibre preform.

The preform was made by winding fibre tows onto a steel plate to $\sim 10 \text{ mm}$ thickness. This was then heated at $\sim 600^\circ\text{C}$. for 30 minutes and transferred to a preheated ($\sim 450^\circ\text{C}$) die. Liquid aluminium alloy at $\sim 850^\circ\text{C}$. was introduced into the die chamber and hydraulic pressure (a few MPa) applied to infiltrate the preform. After a few seconds, a higher pressure was applied ($\sim 25 \text{ MPa}$) to assist consolidation. Heat treatment was based upon previous studies [3] and consisted of solutionising at 550°C . for 8 hours, quenching into cold water, and then artificially ageing at $170 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$. for 2 hours.

TESTING

Specimen dimensions were adapted from ASTM D3552-77, which recommends that the cross section should contain a minimum of 200 filaments. This condition was readily satisfied for longitudinal specimens using a cross-section of width 6 mm and depth 3 mm. For transverse specimens the dimensions were width 8 mm and depth 3 mm, samples being prepared with fibres, firstly, perpendicular and, secondly, parallel to the width. Test coupons were 65 mm long with a gauge length of 30 mm, had soft aluminium end tabs to minimise grip damage during testing and strain gauges mounted in the centre section at 0° and 90° to the direction of applied load. They were machined from composite in both the as-cast and heat-treated (peak-aged) condition. The testing was carried out on an Instron 1195 machine using a cross-head speed of 1.0 mm/min, a minimum of three specimens being tested per condition.

Prior to testing, the edge of a specimen was polished to a fine metallographic finish. It was then examined at different stages of the test by light microscopy and scanning electron microscopy (SEM). SEM fractography was also carried out on tested specimens.

Figure 1. Transverse section of the composite.

RESULTS

Light microscopy of a transverse section, Fig.1, showed that the composite was well consolidated, with an even distribution of fibres of volume fraction ~0.4.

LONGITUDINAL FIBRE ORIENTATION

Stress-strain curves for as-cast and heat-treated composite are shown in Fig. 2. Young' moduli derived from the curves were 130 GPa and 160 GPa respectively, values which are not significantly different in view of the large experimental scatter. Only one Poisson's ratio has been measured since the same Poisson's effect will be expected in any plane parallel to the fibre direction, that is $\nu_{12} = \nu_{13}$, where the first subscript indicates the loading direction and, second relates to the direction of Poisson's contraction (see Fig. 3). Mean data and standard deviations are collated in Table 1. Both curves exhibit a change in slope, referred to as the 'knee point' [4]. Examination of the polished edges of specimens showed that slip lines were developed in the matrix beyond the 'knee point', see Fig. 3a showing slip lines of ~10 μm spacing which stop short a few μm from fibres. Since, therefore, the slip line pattern is clearly associated with matrix yield, the values of stress at the 'knee point' are referred to as yield stress in Table 1. The stresses relating to as-cast and heat-treated composites are 55 MPa and 230 MPa respectively. With increase in applied stress, the slip lines increased in number and there was evidence of duplex slip. The fibres remained undamaged and well bonded to the matrix until the final stages of composite failure, at stresses of 242 MPa and 400 MPa, respectively. Fig. 4b, taken from the failed region of a specimen, shows fibre fracture together with matrix slip lines which now extend up to the fibre/matrix interface. SEM of a fracture surface of as-cast composite revealed brittle failure of fibres and ductile failure of matrix, Fig. 5a; the heat-treated composite showed increased matrix brittleness, Fig. 5b. In both conditions, the broken fibres exhibited hardly any pull-out, although there was evidence of fibre fragmentation close to the fracture surface.

Figure 2. Stress-strain curves for longitudinal fibre orientation.

Figure 3. Fibre orientation and system of co-ordinates.

Table 1. Test results for longitudinal fibre orientation

Material condition	Young's modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Strain to failure(%)	Poisson's ratio, ν_{12}
as-cast	130 \pm 15	55 \pm 10	242 \pm 40	0.26 \pm 0.05	0.31 \pm 0.01
heat-treated	160 \pm 30	230 \pm 30	400 \pm 80	0.30 \pm 0.14	0.31 \pm 0.01

Figure 4. Polished edges of specimens showing matrix slip lines which (a) stop short of the fibre/matrix interface of unbroken fibres and (b) extend right up to a broken fibre.

Figure 5. Fracture surfaces, (a) as-cast and, (b) heat-treated composite.

TRANSVERSE FIBRE ORIENTATION

Stress-strain curves for transverse specimens tested with fibres parallel to the width of the gauge section are reproduced in Fig. 6. The stress-strain response was much the same when the transverse specimens were tested with the fibres perpendicular to the width of the section. From the curves, the transverse modulus was estimated to be ~100 GPa. The yield stress of as-cast composite was 70 MPa and this was found to increase to 130 MPa after heat treatment. Slip lines in the matrix were observed and there was evidence of duplex slip at higher stresses. The as-cast composite fractured at a stress of 160 MPa, with a strain of 0.5%, and heat-treated material fractured at a stress of 203 MPa with a strain to failure of 0.18%. Collated data and standard deviations are given in Table 2. Fracture surfaces showed similar features to those seen on longitudinal specimens, that is some ductile fracture in the matrix of as-cast composite and more brittle characteristics after heat treatment.

Table 2. Test results for transverse fibre orientation

Material condition	Modulus (GPa)	Yield stress (MPa)	Strength (MPa)	Strain to failure(%)	Poisson's ratio	
					ν_{21}	ν_{23}
as-cast	96 ± 5	70 ± 5	160 ± 10	0.50 ± 0.06	0.18 ± 0.01	0.35 ± 0.03
heat-treated	110 ± 5	130 ± 10	203 ± 30	0.18 ± 0.02	0.22 ± 0.01	0.34 ± 0.03

Figure 6. Stress-strain curves for transverse fibre orientation.

DISCUSSION

We shall begin by considering the elastic properties of the composite and comparing data derived from stress-strain measurements with theoretical predictions for modulus and Poisson's ratio. This is followed by an analysis of yield behaviour and final failure.

ELASTIC BEHAVIOUR

The longitudinal Young's modulus (E_1) of the composite may be calculated using the 'Rule of Mixtures' (ROM) relationship,

$$E_1 = E_f V_f + E_m (1 - V_f), \quad (1)$$

where E_f and E_m are Young's modulus of fibre and matrix respectively, and V_f is the fibre volume fraction. If we then substitute the manufacturer's figure of ~210 GPa for E_f , our previous experimental value of 72 GPa for E_m [5], and take $V_f = 0.4$, we obtain a value of 130 GPa for E_1 . This figure agrees well with the modulus derived from the stress-strain data, Table 1, from which it may be concluded that fibre and matrix were contributing fully to the modulus and that the interface bond was strong.

The transverse Young's modulus, E_2 , can be estimated by considering fibre and matrix contributions in series,

$$1 / E_2 = (1 - V_f) / E_m + V_f / E_f. \quad (2)$$

Substituting again the above values gives $E_2 = 95$ GPa. This is virtually identical to the measured modulus of 96 MPa, which demonstrates that, as well as increasing the longitudinal modulus, the fibres improve the transverse modulus to an extent which compares favourably with that achieved with a typical particulate-reinforced aluminium alloy [6].

Poisson's ratio for the longitudinal specimen may be calculated using a ROM expression of the type given in Eqn (1). Thus taking Poisson's ratio as 0.30 for the matrix [5] and 0.24 for the

alumina fibre [6], gives $\nu_{12} = 0.28$. The experimental measurement of 0.31 (Table 1) shows good agreement with this value.

With regard to Poisson's ratio for the transverse specimen, there are two values which are of interest, ν_{21} in the plane of the fibres and ν_{23} in the perpendicular plane. We shall begin by expressing ν_{21} as,

$$\nu_{21} = [V_f \nu_f + (1 - V_f) \nu_m] E_2 / E_1 \quad (3)$$

which, after substituting the appropriate values, gives $\nu_{21} = 0.20$; this is close to the value obtained from experimental measurements, 0.18, see Table 2. Next, an expression for ν_{23} can be derived by considering the overall volume of the composite under the transverse stress [7],

$$i.e. \quad \nu_{23} = 1 - \nu_{21} - E_2 / 3K_c, \quad (4)$$

where K_c , the bulk modulus of the composite, may be expressed as

$$K_c = [V_f / K_f + (1 - V_f) / K_m]^{-1} \text{ with} \quad (5)$$

$$K_f = E_f / [3(1 - 2\nu_f)] \text{ and}$$

$$K_m = E_m / [3(1 - 2\nu_m)].$$

The values calculated for K_f and K_m are 135 GPa and 58 GPa, respectively, which when substituted into Eqn (5) gives 75 MPa for K_c . From Eqn (4) we then have $\nu_{23} = 0.37$, which again matches closely the experimental measurement of 0.35. The value for ν_{23} is significantly larger than Poisson's ratio for the matrix (~ 0.3), but this is not surprising in view of the fact that ν_{21} was only ~ 0.2 . The result further demonstrates that fibres must be well bonded to the matrix.

PLASTIC BEHAVIOUR AND FINAL FAILURE

We shall consider first as-cast composite and then proceed to discuss heat-treated material. For the longitudinal specimen, the 'knee point' in the stress-strain curve marked the stress at which plastic deformation of the matrix began, as evidenced by the slip-line development visible on polished edges of specimens undergoing testing. The stress at the 'knee point' was 55 MPa, which was surprising since calculation of the matrix stress, assuming strains are equal in fibre and matrix, gave a value of only ~ 30 MPa. We thus conclude that the difference between the two values is a consequence of matrix residual stresses caused by differential contraction between fibre and matrix during composite manufacture. Since in the longitudinal direction, the residual stresses in the matrix are tensile, a lower measured yield stress is obtained, the difference being comparable with the average residual stresses of ~ 20 MPa reported in a composite [8].

With increased stress, the density of slip lines progressively increased while the fibres remained undamaged, as indicated by the linear slope of the stress-strain curve. A low rate of matrix strain-hardening was evident which, if we ignore, allows us to equate E_m with zero in Eqn (1). This then gives a value of ~ 85 GPa for E_1 and, although not a truly elastic property since we are in the yield region, it is commensurate with the slope of the curve. As the stress was increased further, the extension of slip lines to the fibre surfaces often led to fibre/matrix debonding and fibre breakage as stresses in these regions of the matrix were relieved by plastic flow. These damage processes were not uniformly distributed throughout the gauge length but were

concentrated in a small region, $\sim 100 \mu\text{m}$, thus producing a local strain sufficiently large to fracture the fibre and lead to failure of the composite. The measured failure strain, 0.3%, was much less than the failure strain of a fibre, 0.8% according to the manufacturer, because the strain gauge value was averaged over a large region (5 mm).

The stress measured at failure of the composite was 242 MPa. If, however, we were to calculate composite strength (σ_1) using a ROM approach,

$$\sigma_1 = \sigma_f V_f + \sigma_m (1 - V_f), \quad (6)$$

where σ_f and σ_m are fibre and matrix strengths respectively, we would obtain a value of 800 MPa. (Here the manufacturer's value of 1.8 GPa was substituted for σ_f and σ_m was taken as 170 MPa [5]). The measured strength is significantly lower than the value calculated from Eqn (6) because (a) there is a local concentration of stress in the region of fracture (see above) and/or (b) the fibre strength is less than the manufacturer's value. Indeed, if we were to substitute a value of ~ 400 MPa for σ_f in Eqn (6), a value for σ_1 close to the measured value of 242 MPa would be obtained. Such a reduction in fibre strength is comparable with that measured for Nicalon fibre when used for reinforcing aluminium alloy [9] and it should, perhaps, be pointed out that we have observed that most of the loss in fibre strength which occurs during composite manufacture appears to be associated with preform manufacture.

Considering, next, transverse composite specimens, the higher yield stress compared with unreinforced alloy, 70 MPa and 55 MPa respectively [5], is again ascribed to compressive residual stresses but now they act in opposition to the applied load. The absence of a clearly-defined 'knee point' in the stress-strain curves and the obvious non-linearity of the curve during yielding is consistent with the strain-hardening response of aluminium, with the slip lines showing duplex slip indicative of stage II work hardening. Such behaviour in transverse specimens is not surprising since fibres in this orientation would have little constraining effect on matrix flow. Moreover, the similarity of the failure strength with that of unreinforced alloy, ~ 170 MPa, further confirms the strong bond which has been developed between fibre and matrix during processing.

Heat treatment of the composite to matrix peak hardness condition resulted in a substantial increase in yield stress, to 230 MPa for longitudinal specimens and to 130 MPa for transverse specimens. These values are $\sim 40\%$ lower than those calculated after substituting the reported yield strength of 263 MPa for unreinforced heat-treated alloy [5] into the ROM formula, which would suggest that the heat treatment has not been fully effective. A possible explanation for the deficiency is that the magnesium which would have segregated the fibre, as previously observed in these composite systems [3], has resulted in the matrix level of magnesium close to the fibres being reduced to such a level that zones are formed which are denuded in precipitate. These zones would, therefore, yield more readily under stress. The effect would be more marked when the stress was applied perpendicularly to the fibres, as was indeed observed with the transverse specimens. With regard to composite strength, this also was increased by heat treatment without the full potential of the matrix being realised. The next stage of this investigation will, therefore, involve optimisation of matrix composition and heat treatment in order to achieve a more effective distribution of age-hardening precipitates in the composites.

CONCLUSIONS

Liquid metal infiltration has been successfully used to make composite of aluminium alloy (6061) reinforced with continuous Altex fibre ($V_f \sim 0.4$). It was well-consolidated and had elastic

properties which matched 'Rule of Mixtures' predictions, with Young's moduli of ~130 GPa and ~100 GPa parallel and perpendicular to the fibres respectively. Poisson's ratio was also in agreement with predictions. The results from these, and other experiments, such as microstructural studies during and after testing, were proof of the strong bond that existed between fibre and matrix.

The differences in yield stress found in directions parallel and perpendicular to the fibres were attributed to anisotropic residual stresses in the matrix. The longitudinal strength of as-cast composite was 400 MPa, although the value may have been affected by a reduction in fibre strength during preform manufacture. The transverse strength of the material matched that of unreinforced alloy.

Heat treatment of the composite to peak hardness (matrix) increased significantly the yield stress and strength but did not achieve full expectations.

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REFERENCES

1. Prangnell, P.B. and Stobbs, W.M., The effect of internal stresses on precipitation behaviour in particulate reinforced Al matrix MMCs. In *Metal Matrix Composites-Processing, Microstructure and Properties* (ed. N.Hansen, D.Juul Jensen, T.Leffers, H.Lilholt, T.Lorentzen, A.S.Pedersen, O.B.Pedersen and B.Ralph) pp.603-610, Risø, 1991.
2. Friend, C.M. and Luxton, S.D., The effect of δ alumina fibre arrays on the age-hardening characteristics of an Al-Mg-Si alloy. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 23 (1988), 3173-317.
3. J.B.Shamsul, N.Jomin, R.S.Bushby and V.D.Scott Fabrication, microstructure and ageing characteristics of an aluminium alloy (6061) reinforced with Altex fibre., *Advances in Materials and Minerals Resources '94* (eds. A.Rahmat, S.Bahn and P.R.Khangaonkar) pp289-298, University Sains Malaysia; Perak, 1994.
4. Piggott, M.R., *Load bearing fibre composites*, pp. 199-201, Pergamon, Oxford, 1980.
5. Chen, A.S., Smith, J., Bushby, R.S., Phillips, M.G. and Scott, V.D., Tensile property evaluation of continuous fibre MMC, *Advanced Composites Letters*, Vol 3 No 3, 1994, 99-102.
6. Clyne, T.W. and Withers, P.J., *An Introduction to Metal Matrix Composites*, Cambridge University Press: Cambridge, 1993.
7. Clyne, T.W., A compressibility-based derivation of simple expressions for the transverse Poisson's ratio and shear modulus of an aligned long fibre composite. *J. Mater. Sci. Lett.*, 9 (1990), 336-339.
8. Withers, P.J., Stobbs, W.M. and Pedersen, O.B., The application of the Eshelby method of internal stress determination for short fibre metal matrix composites. *Acta Metall.*, 37 (1989), 3061-3084.
9. Chapman, A.R., Bleay, S.M. and Scott, V.D., Influence of microstructure on the strength of Nicalon-reinforced aluminium metal-matrix composites. *J. Mater. Sci.*, 29 (1994), 4523-4534.